

Short Communication

Awareness of Counseling Psychology and the Significance of Counseling Service for the Graduate Studies

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Abstract: The study focused about students' Mental Health Wellness from the psychological aspect and social psychological perspectives, as well as the study mainly investigated to identify challenges and complexities faced by the university students. In the study, the researcher was interested in exploring the following question: how important is Psychological Counseling in the university student community? The main objective of the study was to identify awareness among the university undergraduate community on Psychological Counseling. Because of the recent demographic and societal changes, undergraduates encounter several particular difficulties. The greatest degree of expertise in psychological counseling represented fewer than 10%. Up to 23% of the respondents had less in-depth understanding of the topic. Up to 27% of respondents seeking therapy at the institution are those with less knowledge. 33% of the students in the university's internal environment have suffered from some mental issue and 92% of students' do not reach psychological counseling. Findings show the importance of conducting relevant programs for undergraduates in every year at the university and building up the awareness of counseling psychology.

Keywords: Counseling awareness, Counseling service, Psychological counseling, Undergraduate.

I. Introduction

The study looked at the value of counseling services for graduate undergraduates in the context of Sri Lankan universities. Undergraduates typically work in a setting with less assistance and guidance (Hyun, et al., 2006). Passing the important competitive exam and becoming a member of the university community might be difficult for the undergraduate in certain ways. A young person can be identified as a high achiever in education even though they spend some important waking hours in their lives. Graduate undergraduates are more likely than in the past to be entering graduate school with a variety of financial and familial obligations. The university years can also be seen of as a time when a person is transitioning from adolescent to manhood and

beginning to take on social responsibility. However, the issue of diversity is constantly raised among university undergraduates, and there are several reports that those undergraduates who struggle with it confuse crucial facets of their academic and personal lives.

There are too many obligations and responsibilities for undergraduates in university life (Hyun, et al., 2006). The ability to adapt to a new culture should be cultivated independently by undergraduates; this is what sociologists refer to as the socialization process. The study's primary aims are to discover issues that university undergraduates encounter in counselling process in university context. And as a result, to determine whether, as anticipated, the physiological alleviation received from the university counseling service.

The extent to which this complex process is significant to university undergraduates was something the researcher intended to investigate in the study. As evidenced by the recent rise in the prevalence of most emotional issues. At university counseling services, relationship issues were the most often reported issues prior to 1994, but following that year, stress/anxiety issues predominated (Storrie et al., 2009). These conditions have been found among the university population in Sri Lanka. This includes a review of the supporting literature, the study's methodology, and a wider discussion of the research's findings, conclusions, and researcher-proposed recommendations.

II. Research Background

The study conducted a sociological analysis of the significance of psychological counseling in the population of university undergraduates. We now view counseling in our comments as a career-oriented topic with a strong professional responsibility for its service and as the foundation for professional welfare, social welfare, and social security while preserving professional ethics. With reference to the philosophers who pioneered the origins and evolution of counseling as well as the widely discussed subject of counseling, this article aims to provide in depth, under the heading of the literature review, the theory and idea presented in the development of the subject. In order to solve the wide range of issues that a person in a particular social system is inevitably faced with, it is sometimes essential to ask for another person's assistance. You might think of psychological counseling as a method that meets that are in need of (Borgen, 1984). The interaction between both the counselor as well as the agent is another way to define counseling. This connection may exist between two persons, or even more than two in specific circumstances. It seeks to make the performer's thoughts and understandings clear over his lifetime, help him select the significant modifications he desires, and help him deal with emotional and interpersonal issues. University of Colombo delivers majorly Bachelor Degrees and Honours Degrees for undergraduates and the study programme continues all five weekdays and there are assignments, quizzes, presentations, midterm tests and end examinations in every year to archive and complete for obtain the degree.

Eisenberg et al. (2011) and Eisenberg et al. (2012) state few key factors regarding Awareness of Counseling Psychology and the Significance of Counseling Service for the Graduate Studies. Utilizing and modifying the counselling services for undergraduates has been advanced among those studies. Overall, the findings indicate that help-seeking for mental health varies substantially across student characteristics and across campuses. Strategies to address the low prevalence of treatment will need to be responsive to this diversity.

III. Methodology

Questionnaires, Observation, Case studies and interviews are used to collect primary data of this study. The main research field was University of Colombo and Faculty of Science, Faculty of Arts, Faculty of Management and Finance and Faculty of Law were selected for the study the sample was 100 undergraduates and the sample method was Non random sampling. Data analysis was carried out under thematic analysis. Due to the lack of a

counseling center for the faculty, the study was limited to 4 faculties and the conscientious client's reluctance to mention their personal matters made it difficult to obtain accurate information through the negotiation process.

IV. Findings and Discussion

There are a number of factors that led the researcher to study the need and importance of Psychological Counseling at the University of Colombo. As a university undergraduate, the experience gained during the undergraduate term and the information obtained through contact with the University Counseling Center set the stage for it. In terms of the analytical dimension, the results and discussion include the relationship of counseling and psychology, the awareness of the university undergraduate community, the awareness and advocacy of counseling services, the likelihood of the undergraduate being confused, the confusion that the undergraduate faces, as well as the university environment and beyond. The broader focus of the researcher was to discuss the essential factors for counseling and the tendency for non-counseling to persist despite the disturbing emotional disturbances. The researcher has tended to make a proportionate and quantitative presentation on issues such as the Counseling Center and the University's consultant awareness. The researcher has also focused on the likelihood of counseling on gender.

V. Awareness on Psychological Counseling and Counseling Service

A quantitative examination of the current demand for and awareness of psychological counseling in the undergraduate body of the University of Colombo initially looked at the awareness of the undergraduates in these faculties in the psychology and counseling topic. Here are some quantitative statistics about undergraduates' knowledge of psychology and counseling from the four faculties chosen for the study. Out of the four faculties, faculties of Arts undergraduates are more knowledgeable about psychological counseling.

The most significant statistic is that 23% of individuals do not know what psychological counseling is. An important fact is that only around 10% of individuals have any experience with therapy. The faculty as a whole does have some grasp of psychology and counseling, despite the fact that it is quite limited. Only one in ten undergraduates in the scientific faculty are clueless, compared to the 27% percent of undergraduates who do not know anything about psychological counseling.

It has been determined that the existence of a psychological therapy facility inside the faculty's limits was the cause of this. The university undergraduate has a highly demanding and hectic study environment, and they are upset that they cannot focus on such things because of the existing educational system and the university administration is not taking a close look at it. The qualitative data collected serves as additional confirmation of this. *"Counseling is crucial for undergraduates, in my opinion. The majority of undergraduates I know have issues, yet they seldom seek counseling. Both the counseling center's address and the counseling office's location are unknown to them. I've never gone to a counseling program or session on campus. A campus session on counseling has never been communicated to me."*

Table 1: Awareness of Counseling Service

		Awareness of Counseling Service				Total
		Excellent	good	normal	Poor	
faculty	Arts	7	5	14	14	40
	Management	1	4	16	9	30
	Law	2	6	9	3	20
	Science	1	7	1	1	10
Total		11	22	40	27	100

According to the table above, only 11% of university undergraduates have a good understanding when it comes to their awareness of the counseling services of university undergraduates.

VI. The Environment of Facing Psychological Problems

Some individuals are struggling in the collegiate setting, while others struggle in a dorm, in private housing, or in their immediate surroundings. The undergraduates of the sample are currently belongs to University of Colombo and they are from different cultures, religions and classes. There are times when undergraduates experience issues in their families, communities, or cities, and these issues can spark arguments on campus and elsewhere. According to the data, 33% of undergraduates having issues in a university setting, 8% in a residential issues (water issues, uncomforted settings and food issues), in hostel setting, and 9% having issues in family or personal setting. One of the major issues undergraduates encounter in the university setting is their fear of being sexually assaulted because of the social knowledge they obtain through mistaken notions. in their first year as well as their dread of admission since they worry about being bullied there. Additionally, this study has found multiple cases of Colombo University undergraduates dealing with stress because of the work load and study goals.

VII. Referring the Counseling Service

The respondents are having a variety of psychological issues because of the academic and family issues. The findings show that there are several conflicts of interest involving the educational system, yet there are very few consultants and Counsellors working for undergraduates. Undergraduates who sought therapy for academic concerns made up 8% of the undergraduate population. Even though there is a Psychological Counseling center at the University of Colombo, there is no interest for undergraduates to get into it and they do not know about Psychological Counseling or counseling service. As the study results, undergraduates are less likely to meet the university advisor even though they are mentally ill due to problems with the education system. The reasons for this seem to be that undergraduates are unaware of the counseling center and the counselor. It was also revealed that although some undergraduates were aware of the counseling center, they had no knowledge of the counselor.

VIII. Awareness of the Counselor and Counseling Center

The results obtained through the analysis of the data, undergraduates' understanding and awareness of the counselor employed by the counseling center are as follows. Awareness of the counselor revealed that 9% had a good understanding, 14% said they had some understanding, 19% had a general understanding and 58% had no understanding. The above cases clearly illustrate that the data provided by randomly selected undergraduates for the study, as much as 50%, have no knowledge of the counseling center and 58% are unaware of the counselor. According to the data, the knowledge of the counseling center and the instructor is very low in almost all the faculties.

The knowledge of the Psychological Counseling Center is very low in all three faculties of Arts, Management and Law. According to data available at the Faculty of Science, the level of awareness of the Counseling Center of the Faculty of Science is very high compared to the other faculties. That is, out of the ten undergraduates selected in the Faculty, three are very knowledgeable, four are well-informed and two are of general knowledge. The key factor is that the Counseling Center is located at the Faculty of Science where the faculty and undergraduates are aware of the center and the counselor.

IX. The probability of having problems and counseling in terms of gender

Another important issue that has been revealed in the study is the probability that the undergraduates of Colombo University face problems in terms of gender. Analysing and understanding the issues of

undergraduates under gender based perspective have become a major issue while taking counselling. People who describe and adding values to people stresses undergraduates in order to gender difference. Especially men are being criticized on personality and strength while taking counselling and they meant to be “Losers” of men take counselling. Women get criticized from the people on taking counselling and it added negative values for their relationship, marriage and personality. Thus undergraduate have to face gender based issues while taking counselling and counselling services couldn't address this issue properly under their service quality.

X. Mental Conditions of the Undergraduates and need of meeting the Counselor.

Undergraduates of the University of Colombo face various problems in the university environment. Problems that a person may have in everyday life can be summarized under three sources. They are Biological problems, Psychological problems, and Sociological issues (Kamunyu et al, 2016). According to the Case Studies, Conflict with senior groups creates mental confusion over problems encountered when building relationships with them. Undergraduates are facing emotional distress due to shyness and fear of anxiety, loss of sense, fear of returning to home University translations from family and relatives living in the area. Many of the undergraduates are not experiencing a comfortable atmosphere at the university because of the stress made by seniors and overloaded work in the academic process. Also the case studies highlight some key points that make undergraduates mental condition weaker and stressful in the university life. The language issue and the ethnic exclusion among the undergraduates, class conflict among the undergraduates, less supportive teaching methods and overload work, food and water is not familiar and comfortable, cost of living, cultural gaps and collapse, routine changes, need of caring and love and strange behaviors of peer groups. Those conditions are stressing the undergraduate and they mostly got addicted or shaped by the conditions forcefully. The need of meeting a counselor hasn't become a major solution among undergraduates for making their life and mental condition in a safe hand.

XI. Conclusion

One of the main conclusions is that the undergraduate community of the University of Colombo is that there is little understanding of psychology and counseling. Management, Science, Law and other faculties can include Counselling as a subject discipline or a core practice of their main stream in order to increase awareness of Psychological Counseling at least in the Colombo University undergraduate community. The second conclusion the researcher makes from the study is that the university undergraduate population is less aware of Psychological Counseling. In this conclusion, it is important to note that all four faculties, Faculty of Management, Faculty of Management, Faculty of Law and Faculty of Arts, have a low level of awareness of the services available. The researcher points out that the lack of awareness among the undergraduate community about the Psychological Counseling service at the University of Colombo is very problematic. In an attempt to overcome this situation, the researcher suggests that the counseling center should be located in an environment conducive to all the academic faculties located in the University of Colombo.

The university's medical center not demanding ethics or conformability and therefore undergraduates cannot access privacy while creating credible ideas for the undergraduates. To ensure better awareness and interest in Psychological Counseling and counseling in the university undergraduate community, it is mandatory for all faculties to conduct workshops conducted by the Consultant Center within the university premises and once a month compulsory awareness workshops are held. Undergraduates should be able to meet with the instructor in secret or by telephone. In such workshops, the consultant should follow some methodology to gain the confidence of those who are in trouble.

Despite the fact that the university community has some psychological difficulties in getting psychological counseling, the lack of awareness of the counseling center and the lack of trust in the counselor does not

necessarily lead to counseling. It is pointed out that the need to organize programs to educate undergraduates about the long-term consequences of mental illness and the subsequent adverse consequences, because of the long-lasting effects of psychological crises and the failure of the individual to avoid counseling. Researchers also suggest that psychological counseling service trust programs should be mandated as a matter of professional trust, with professional ethics of counseling.

The researcher comes to the conclusion that there is insufficient knowledge about romantic relationships and safe sex in the university undergraduate population. The researcher points out that it is compulsory to have adequate sexual counseling among the youth who are selected to universities. The researcher proposes to conduct workshops on sexual counseling, representing undergraduates each year at the university. It shows the importance of conducting such programs for undergraduates every year at the university and taking the attitude of the university undergraduates as a back-up. Another important conclusion from the study is the fact that university undergraduates feel strongly about home (home sick). In the university community, undergraduates feel strongly about home, the stress of exams, the stress of not being able to hand over the assignment date, and the mental disorganization caused by the failure of the exams. Recognizing the frequent mental confusion and turmoil that the university undergraduate community faces, the researcher finally suggests that the administration structure intervene and provide some cultural and literary value-added programs and programs for a period of time for the undergraduates' psychological well-being providing necessary arrangements for the work.

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